

Beauty of Magic Squares: 540-Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 20, 30, 42, 56 and 72

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=9176>

Abstract

*This paper presents a systematic construction of **multiple order bordered magic squares** at orders 20, 30, 42, 56, and 72. for a full structural summary). Unlike classical block-wise bordered magic squares, which are built as multiples of a single block size, the structures explored here incorporate successive borders drawn from magic squares of **different** orders — specifically orders 3 through 8 — each contributing a distinct structural layer.*

*The innermost core is a magic square of order 12 formed by different-sum magic squares of order 3. Successive borders of orders 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8 are then applied; **even-order borders** consist of **equal-sum**, while **odd-order borders** consist of **different-sum** magic squares. In case of order 8, first three are of equal-sums and last three are of different sums. The combinatorial multiplicity of border types at each level yields a hierarchy of distinct configurations:*

The further study of multiple order bordered magic squares of orders 90, 108, 110, 120, 132 and 144 are given in details in the reference list.

Keywords: magic squares, bordered magic squares, pandiagonal magic squares, block-wise construction, multiple order borders, combinatorial enumeration, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

A **magic square** of order n is an arrangement of n^2 distinct integers in an $n \times n$ grid such that the sums of each row, each column, and both main diagonals are equal. This common value is called the **magic constant** (or magic sum), usually denoted S . For a magic square containing the consecutive integers $1, 2, \dots, n^2$, the magic constant is

$$S = \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2}. \tag{1}$$

Magic squares have fascinated mathematicians, artists, and philosophers for millennia, appearing in ancient texts. Two constructions are central to the present work.

Definition 1.1 (Bordered magic square). *A magic square is said to be **bordered** if the removal of any outermost border of cells leaves a smaller magic square. All entries are consecutive integers.*

Definition 1.2 (Block-wise bordered magic square). *A magic square is **block-wise bordered** if each border layer is not a single cell wide but is composed of smaller magic squares used as building blocks.*

During past years author [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [17, 18, 19]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a

prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [20, 21, 22, 23]. Some connection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [25, 26, 27, 28, 29]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are separated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White's web-site [3].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White's web-site [3] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [11, 12, 3].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [30].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [32].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [34].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [36].
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [38].
- **Thirteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 13 [40].
- **Fifteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 15 [42].
- **Seventeen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 17 [44].
- **Nineteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 19 [46].

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [74, 75, 76, 77, 77, 78, 79].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [25, 31].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [26, 33].

- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [27, 35].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [28, 37].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [29, 39].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [41].
- **Sixteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 16 [43].
- **Eighteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 18 [45].
- **Twenty Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 20 [47].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

The aim of this work is to bring multiple order **bordered** magic squares of orders 20, 30, 42, 56 and 72. Let see below how it is done.

See below the details of above multiple order bordered magic square.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**

1. Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.

- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**

1. In this case, we have considered two types of magic squares of order 4.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

- (b) The second is formed by two equal sums magic sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 resulting in a magic square of order 4. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 20

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**

1. In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.

- (a) The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.

- (c) The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30

- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**

1. In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.

- (a) The first is normal magic square of order 6.

- (b) The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

- (c) The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42

- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**

1. In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.

- (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

- (b) The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .

- (c) The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .

- (d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.
- (e) The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 1. In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.
 - (a) The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 - (b) The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.
 - (c) The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
 - (d) The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width,we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.
 - (e) The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.
 - (f) The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

Below summarises the six construction levels.

- **0 Border: Different sums magic squares of order 3**
 - Initially, we have a magic square of order 12 formed by different sums magic squares of order 3.
- **1st Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 4**
 - In this case we have considered two different types of magic squares of order 4. Combining with magic square of order 12 we have 2-different types of magic squares of order 20.

- **2nd Border: Different sums magic squares of order 5**
 - In this case, we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 5. Combining with 3 magic squares of order 20 we have 6-different types of magic squares of order 20.
- **3rd Border: Equal sums magic squares of order 6**
 - In this case also we have considered 3-different types of magic squares of order 6. Combining with 6 magic squares of order 30 we have 18-different types of magic squares of order 42.
- **4th Border: Different sums magic squares of order 7.**
 - In this case, we have considered 5-different ways of magic squares of order 7. Combining with 18 magic squares of order 42 we have 90-different types of magic squares of order 56.
- **5th Border: Equal and different sums magic squares of order 8**
 - In this case we have considered 6 different types of magic squares. Combining with 90 magic squares of order 56 we have 540-different types of magic squares of order 72.

The total count at each level equals the product of all variant counts up to that level:

$$N_{\text{ord.72}} = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 5 \times 6 = 540. \quad (2)$$

More details of each border are given in section below with details in each subsection.

2 Multiple Order Bordered Magic Squares

2.1 Magic Square of Order 12

Let's consider a magic square of order 12 given by

12	mgc												870	
		139	144	137	112	117	110	31	36	29	4	9	2	870
		138	140	142	111	113	115	30	32	34	3	5	7	870
		143	136	141	116	109	114	35	28	33	8	1	6	870
		13	18	11	22	27	20	121	126	119	130	135	128	870
		12	14	16	21	23	25	120	122	124	129	131	133	870
		17	10	15	26	19	24	125	118	123	134	127	132	870
		40	45	38	67	72	65	76	81	74	103	108	101	870
		39	41	43	66	68	70	75	77	79	102	104	106	870
		44	37	42	71	64	69	80	73	78	107	100	105	870
		94	99	92	85	90	83	58	63	56	49	54	47	870
		93	95	97	84	86	88	57	59	61	48	50	52	870
		98	91	96	89	82	87	62	55	60	53	46	51	870
		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

It is constructed with different sums magic squares of order 3

3	mgc				15
		4	9	2	15
		3	5	7	15
		8	1	6	15
		15	15	15	15

2.2 Magic Square of Order 20

Below are figures of two magic square of order 20. It is with blocks of order 3 and 4. Blocks of order 3 are forming a magic square of order 12. The border magic squares of order 4 give us a magic square of order 20 in two different ways. One of block of order 4 is a **pandiagonal** and second is based on two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .

20	mgc																			4010	
	7	396	1	398	15	388	9	390	23	380	17	382	31	372	25	374	39	364	33	366	4010
	2	397	8	395	10	389	16	387	18	381	24	379	26	373	32	371	34	365	40	363	4010
	400	3	394	5	392	11	386	13	384	19	378	21	376	27	370	29	368	35	362	37	4010
	393	6	399	4	385	14	391	12	377	22	383	20	369	30	375	28	361	38	367	36	4010
	127	276	121	278	267	272	265	240	245	238	159	164	157	132	137	130	47	356	41	358	4010
	122	277	128	275	266	268	270	239	241	243	158	160	162	131	133	135	42	357	48	355	4010
	280	123	274	125	271	264	269	244	237	242	163	156	161	136	129	134	360	43	354	45	4010
	273	126	279	124	141	146	139	150	155	148	249	254	247	258	263	256	353	46	359	44	4010
	119	284	113	286	140	142	144	149	151	153	248	250	252	257	259	261	55	348	49	350	4010
	114	285	120	283	145	138	143	154	147	152	253	246	251	262	255	260	50	349	56	347	4010
	288	115	282	117	168	173	166	195	200	193	204	209	202	231	236	229	352	51	346	53	4010
	281	118	287	116	167	169	171	194	196	198	203	205	207	230	232	234	345	54	351	52	4010
	111	292	105	294	172	165	170	199	192	197	208	201	206	235	228	233	63	340	57	342	4010
	106	293	112	291	222	227	220	213	218	211	186	191	184	177	182	175	58	341	64	339	4010
	296	107	290	109	221	223	225	212	214	216	185	187	189	176	178	180	344	59	338	61	4010
	289	110	295	108	226	219	224	217	210	215	190	183	188	181	174	179	337	62	343	60	4010
	103	300	97	302	95	308	89	310	87	316	81	318	79	324	73	326	71	332	65	334	4010
	98	301	104	299	90	309	96	307	82	317	88	315	74	325	80	323	66	333	72	331	4010
	304	99	298	101	312	91	306	93	320	83	314	85	328	75	322	77	336	67	330	69	4010
	297	102	303	100	305	94	311	92	313	86	319	84	321	78	327	76	329	70	335	68	4010
	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010

20	mgc																			4010	
	399	2	398	3	391	10	390	11	383	18	382	19	375	26	374	27	367	40	33	362	4010
	8	393	5	396	16	385	13	388	24	377	21	380	32	369	29	372	34	361	368	39	4010
	1	400	4	397	9	392	12	389	17	384	20	381	25	376	28	373	366	37	36	363	4010
	394	7	395	6	386	15	387	14	378	23	379	22	370	31	371	30	35	364	365	38	4010
	279	128	121	274	267	272	265	240	245	238	159	164	157	132	137	130	359	48	41	354	4010
	122	273	280	127	266	268	270	239	241	243	158	160	162	131	133	135	42	353	360	47	4010
	278	125	124	275	271	264	269	244	237	242	163	156	161	136	129	134	358	45	44	355	4010
	123	276	277	126	141	146	139	150	155	148	249	254	247	258	263	256	43	356	357	46	4010
	287	120	113	282	140	142	144	149	151	153	248	250	252	257	259	261	351	56	49	346	4010
	114	281	288	119	145	138	143	154	147	152	253	246	251	262	255	260	50	345	352	55	4010
	286	117	116	283	168	173	166	195	200	193	204	209	202	231	236	229	350	53	52	347	4010
	115	284	285	118	167	169	171	194	196	198	203	205	207	230	232	234	51	348	349	54	4010
	295	112	105	290	172	165	170	199	192	197	208	201	206	235	228	233	343	64	57	338	4010
	106	289	296	111	222	227	220	213	218	211	186	191	184	177	182	175	58	337	344	63	4010
	294	109	108	291	221	223	225	212	214	216	185	187	189	176	178	180	342	61	60	339	4010
	107	292	293	110	226	219	224	217	210	215	190	183	188	181	174	179	59	340	341	62	4010
	303	104	97	298	311	90	310	91	319	82	318	83	327	74	326	75	335	66	334	67	4010
	98	297	304	103	96	305	93	308	88	313	85	316	80	321	77	324	72	329	69	332	4010
	302	101	100	299	89	312	92	309	81	320	84	317	73	328	76	325	65	336	68	333	4010
	99	300	301	102	306	95	307	94	314	87	315	86	322	79	323	78	330	71	331	70	4010
	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010

It is based on the following two types of magic squares of order 4.

	pan	34	34	34	34		4	mgc					34
34	7	12	1	14	34			15	2	14	3	34	
34	2	13	8	11	34			8	9	5	12	34	
34	16	3	10	5	34			1	16	4	13	34	
	9	6	15	4	34			10	7	11	6	34	
	34	34	34	34	34			34	34	34	34	34	

2.3 Magic Square of Order 30

In order to get bordered magic squares of order 30, we used following three different types of magic squares of order 5:

	pan	65	65	65	65	65		5	mgc				65		5	mgc				65	
65	1	7	13	19	25	65			16	11	12	23	3	65		22	25	5	7	6	65
65	18	24	5	6	12	65			9	13	17	25	1	65		2	12	17	10	24	65
65	10	11	17	23	4	65			14	15	10	7	19	65		3	11	13	15	23	65
65	22	3	9	15	16	65			5	6	22	8	24	65		18	16	9	14	8	65
	14	20	21	2	8	65			21	20	4	2	18	65		20	1	21	19	4	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65			65	65	65	65	65	65		65	65	65	65	65	65

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 5.
 1. The first is **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5.
 2. The second is **cornered** magic square of order 5, where there are two **equal sums magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and a magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner.
 3. The third is **single-layer bordered** magic square with magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 30.

Combing with two magic squares of order 20 and three magic squares of order 5 lead us to 6 different types of magic squares of order 30. See below in figures:

30 mgc																														13515	
751	757	763	769	775	676	682	688	694	700	226	232	238	244	250	176	182	188	194	200	26	32	38	44	50	776	782	788	794	800	13515	
768	774	755	756	762	693	699	680	681	687	243	249	230	231	237	193	199	180	181	187	43	49	30	31	37	793	799	780	781	787	13515	
760	761	767	773	754	685	686	692	698	679	235	236	242	248	229	185	186	192	198	179	35	36	42	48	29	785	786	792	798	779	13515	
772	753	759	765	766	697	678	684	690	691	247	228	234	240	241	197	178	184	190	191	47	28	34	40	41	797	778	784	790	791	13515	
764	770	771	752	758	689	695	696	677	683	239	245	246	227	233	189	195	196	177	183	39	45	46	27	33	789	795	796	777	783	13515	
151	157	163	169	175	257	646	251	648	265	638	259	640	273	630	267	632	281	622	275	624	289	614	283	616	726	732	738	744	750	13515	
168	174	155	156	162	252	647	258	645	260	639	266	637	268	631	274	629	276	623	282	621	284	615	290	613	743	749	730	731	737	13515	
160	161	167	173	154	650	253	644	255	642	261	636	263	634	269	628	271	626	277	620	279	618	285	612	287	735	736	742	748	729	13515	
172	153	159	165	166	643	256	649	254	635	264	641	262	627	272	633	270	619	280	625	278	611	288	617	286	747	728	734	740	741	13515	
164	170	171	152	158	377	526	371	528	517	522	515	490	495	488	409	414	407	382	387	380	297	606	291	608	739	745	746	727	733	13515	
1	7	13	19	25	372	527	378	525	516	518	520	489	491	493	408	410	412	381	383	385	292	607	298	605	876	882	888	894	900	13515	
18	24	5	6	12	530	373	524	375	521	514	519	494	487	492	413	406	411	386	379	384	610	293	604	295	893	899	880	881	887	13515	
10	11	17	23	4	523	376	529	374	391	396	389	400	405	398	499	504	497	508	513	506	603	296	609	294	885	886	892	898	879	13515	
22	3	9	15	16	369	534	363	536	390	392	394	399	401	403	498	500	502	507	509	511	305	598	299	600	897	878	884	890	891	13515	
14	20	21	2	8	364	535	370	533	395	388	393	404	397	402	503	496	501	512	505	510	300	599	306	597	889	895	896	877	883	13515	
801	807	813	819	825	538	365	532	367	418	423	416	445	450	443	454	459	452	481	486	479	602	301	596	303	76	82	88	94	100	13515	
818	824	805	806	812	531	368	537	366	417	419	421	444	446	448	453	455	457	480	482	484	595	304	601	302	93	99	80	81	87	13515	
810	811	817	823	804	361	542	355	544	422	415	420	449	442	447	458	451	456	485	478	483	313	590	307	592	85	86	92	98	79	13515	
822	803	809	815	816	356	543	362	541	472	477	470	463	468	461	436	441	434	427	432	425	308	591	314	589	97	78	84	90	91	13515	
814	820	821	802	808	546	357	540	359	471	473	475	462	464	466	435	437	439	426	428	430	594	309	588	311	89	95	96	77	83	13515	
826	832	838	844	850	539	360	545	358	476	469	474	467	460	465	440	433	438	431	424	429	587	312	593	310	51	57	63	69	75	13515	
843	849	830	831	837	353	550	347	552	345	558	339	560	337	566	331	568	329	574	323	576	321	582	315	584	68	74	55	56	62	13515	
835	836	842	848	829	348	551	354	549	340	559	346	557	332	567	338	565	324	575	330	573	316	583	322	581	60	61	67	73	54	13515	
847	828	834	840	841	554	349	548	351	562	341	556	343	570	333	564	335	578	325	572	327	586	317	580	319	72	53	59	65	66	13515	
839	845	846	827	833	547	352	553	350	555	344	561	342	563	336	569	334	571	328	577	326	579	320	585	318	64	70	71	52	58	13515	
101	107	113	119	125	201	207	213	219	225	651	657	663	669	675	701	707	713	719	725	851	857	863	869	875	126	132	138	144	150	13515	
118	124	105	106	112	218	224	205	206	212	668	674	655	656	662	718	724	705	706	712	868	874	855	856	862	143	149	130	131	137	13515	
110	111	117	123	104	210	211	217	223	204	660	661	667	673	654	710	711	717	723	704	860	861	867	873	854	135	136	142	148	129	13515	
122	103	109	115	116	222	203	209	215	216	672	653	659	665	666	722	703	709	715	716	872	853	859	865	866	147	128	134	140	141	13515	
114	120	121	102	108	214	220	221	202	208	664	670	671	652	658	714	720	721	702	708	864	870	871	852	858	139	145	146	127	133	13515	
1	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515	13515

6	mgc						111	6	mgc						111	6	mgc						111
	1	35	34	33	2	6	111		17	22	11	24	29	8	111		32	30	3	36	4	6	111
	30	8	28	9	11	25	111		12	23	18	21	27	10	111		2	17	22	11	24	35	111
	24	23	15	16	20	13	111		26	13	20	15	35	2	111		8	12	23	18	21	29	111
	18	14	21	22	17	19	111		19	16	25	14	9	28	111		10	26	13	20	15	27	111
	7	26	10	27	29	12	111		4	3	36	30	6	32	111		28	19	16	25	14	9	111
	31	5	3	4	32	36	111		33	34	1	7	5	31	111		31	7	34	1	33	5	111
	111	111	111	111	111	111	111		111	111	111	111	111	111	111		111	111	111	111	111	111	111

See the details:

- In this case also we have considered three different types of magic squares of order 6.
 1. The first is normal magic square of order 6.
 2. The second is **cornered** magic square of order 6, where there is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner with two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
 3. The third one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 42.

Combing with 6 magic squares of order 30 and 3 magic squares of order 6 lead us to 18 different types of magic squares of order 42. See below in figures:

These magic squares are composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5 and 6.

2.5 Magic Square of Order 56

In order to get bordered magic squares of order 56, we used following five different types of magic squares of order 7:

	pan	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	7	mgc							175	7	mgc								175
175	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175		4	30	44	32	15	13	37	175		26	21	28	30	20	8	42	175	
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175		46	20	6	18	35	9	41	175		27	25	23	33	17	12	38	175	
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175		34	16	26	21	28	17	33	175		22	29	24	14	36	48	2	175	
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175		42	8	27	25	23	47	3	175		34	32	31	13	15	45	5	175	
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175		43	7	22	29	24	39	11	175		16	18	19	35	37	10	40	175	
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175		1	49	48	12	19	36	10	175		46	49	7	47	6	11	9	175	
	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175		5	45	2	38	31	14	40	175		4	1	43	3	44	41	39	175	
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

7	mgc							175	7	mgc							175
	47	38	11	15	14	37	13	175		42	38	40	5	4	2	44	175
	3	12	39	35	36	6	44	175		1	34	37	17	19	18	49	175
	34	16	28	23	24	30	20	175		3	14	24	29	22	36	47	175
	19	31	21	25	29	10	40	175		43	15	23	25	27	35	7	175
	7	43	26	27	22	42	8	175		41	30	28	21	26	20	9	175
	17	33	4	49	45	9	18	175		39	32	13	33	31	16	11	175
	48	2	46	1	5	41	32	175		6	12	10	45	46	48	8	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 5 different types of magic squares of order 7.
 1. The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.
 2. The second is **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle and 4 equal sums **magic rectangles** of orders 2×3 .
 3. The third is a **cornered** magic square of order 7 composed of another **cornered** magic square of order 5 with magic squares of order 3 at the upper-left corner. Two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×3 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 .
 4. The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 7 with magic square of order 3 in the middle. Also there are four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . This type of magic squares we call as **cyclic-double-layer** magic square of order 7.

5. The fifth is a **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 7, where there is a magic square of order 3 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic squares of order 56.

Combing with 18 magic squares of order 42 and 5 magic squares of order 7 lead us to 90 different types of magic squares of order 56. See below few examples in figures:

There are 90 magic squares of order 56 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7. More details are in an excel file attached with the work.

2.6 Magic Square of Order 72

In order to get **bordered magic squares** of order 72, we used following six different types of magic squares of order 8:

8x8 pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	8 mgc									260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260		31	36	25	38	43	22	13	52	260
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260		26	37	32	35	23	42	1	64	260
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260		40	27	34	29	41	24	54	11	260
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260		33	30	39	28	49	16	9	56	260
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260		18	17	44	50	20	46	7	58	260
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260		47	48	21	15	19	45	53	12	260
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260		10	8	62	51	6	61	60	2	260
	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260		55	57	3	14	59	4	63	5	260
1	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	2	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

8 mgc									260	8 mgc									260
	63	58	8	61	60	1	6	3	260		12	57	56	4	2	64	46	19	260
	2	7	57	4	5	64	59	62	260		53	8	9	61	63	1	47	18	260
	17	48	31	36	25	38	21	44	260		14	51	39	32	25	34	59	6	260
	20	45	26	37	32	35	24	41	260		50	15	26	33	40	31	5	60	260
	47	18	40	27	34	29	43	22	260		48	17	38	29	28	35	16	49	260
	46	19	33	30	39	28	42	23	260		62	3	27	36	37	30	22	43	260
	11	14	9	52	53	16	50	55	260		11	54	45	44	24	23	52	7	260
	54	51	56	13	12	49	15	10	260		10	55	20	21	41	42	13	58	260
3	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	4	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

8	mgc								260	/	8	mgc								260	/			
	8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260			63	8	1	58	55	10	54	11	260				
	5	46	44	17	50	18	20	60	260			2	57	64	7	16	49	13	52	260				
	6	16	31	36	25	38	49	59	260			62	5	4	59	9	56	12	53	260				
	11	22	26	37	32	35	43	54	260			3	60	61	6	50	15	51	14	260				
	61	24	40	27	34	29	41	4	260			39	26	38	27	47	24	17	42	260				
	56	42	33	30	39	28	23	9	260			32	33	29	36	18	41	48	23	260				
	55	45	21	48	15	47	19	10	260			25	40	28	37	46	21	20	43	260				
	58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260			34	31	35	30	19	44	45	22	260				
5								260	/	260	/	6								260	/			
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	/	260	/	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	/

See the details:

- In this case, we have considered 6 different types of magic squares of order 8.
 1. The first is a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 formed by four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.
 2. The second is a **cornered** magic square of order 8, where there is again a **cornered** magic square of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal sums in each case.
 3. The third is a **double-layer bordered** magic square with **pandiagonal** with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. It has 2 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×8 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×4 .
 4. The forth is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 with a magic square of order 4 in the middle. This magic square of order 4 is again composed two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . The magic square of order 4 also have four equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×6 . Since it is formed by only **strips** of equal width, we call it a **striped** magic square of order 8.
 5. The fifth one is four equal sums magic squares of order 4, where each magic square of order 4 is formed by two equal sums **magic rectangles** of order 2×4 . Since it is formed by only magic rectangles of equal width it is known as **striped** magic square.
 6. The sixth one is **single-layer bordered** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This lead us to a **multiple order bordered** magic square of order 72.

Combing 90 magic squares of order 56 and 6 magic squares of order 8 lead us to 540 different types of magic squares of order 72. See below few examples in figures:

There are 540 magic squares of order 72 composed of magic squares orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8. More details are in an excel file attached with the work.

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